

Metacultural competence and ELT curriculum: The case of Iranian undergraduate ELT program

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The present study aims at exploring the representation of metacultural competence (MC)—a competence that allows negotiation of cultural conceptualizations—in the documents designed at policy and planning stages of ELT curriculum development in Iran. For the policy stage, due to lack of an overt foreign language education policy document, seven major policy documents of Iran (namely, *20-year National Vision*, *Comprehensive Science Roadmap*, *Support for Comprehensive Science Roadmap in the Domain of Languages*, *Cultural Engineering Document*, *National Curriculum*, *Fundamental Reform in Education*, and *Islamicization of Universities*) were selected. For the planning stage, Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students were chosen. Content analysis of the selected documents revealed that the analyzed documents did not represent MC in detail and mostly attended to the ‘cultural variation awareness’ component and the ‘acknowledge’ and ‘anticipate’ principles, which were limited to negotiating Islamic ideology and disregarded Iranian cultural conceptualizations.

Keywords: ELT Curriculum; Foreign Language Education Policy (FLEP); Iran; Metacultural Competence; National Policy Documents; Undergraduate ELT Program

1. Introduction

According to Kirkpatrick (2012), the content of ELT curriculum should represent not only the “information about the cultures of the people with whom the learners will be communicating . . . , but also the cultural values that they themselves hold dear.” (p. 38). These ‘cultural values’ pertain to the way English language learners around the world conceptualize meanings, events, and concepts reflected in the incorporation of their local cultural conceptualizations, a collective term to refer to ‘cultural schema’, ‘cultural metaphor’, and ‘cultural category’ (see Sharifian, 2017), in using English as an

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International Language (EIL) or World Englishes (WEs) (Sadeghpour & Sharifian, 2021; Sharifian, 2009). Accordingly, ELT curriculum research awaits investigation in terms of specifying the represented competence in English in light of a model that covers dynamicity and heterogeneity of language-culture nexus and the subsequent complexities of the current use of English. It seems that Sharifian's (2013b, 2018a,b) metacultural competence (MC) may set the platform for such an investigation. As an offspring of the multidisciplinary field of Cultural Linguistics that explores the interrelationship between language and cultural conceptualizations (see Sharifian, 2017), MC enables interlocutors to negotiate their own cultural conceptualizations and understand others' in light of the heterogeneously distributed cultural cognition among people of a speech community within a particular culture (Sharifian, 2011, 2015).

However, the study of any ELT curriculum without considering Foreign Language Education Policy (FLEP) component may provide an incomplete picture since, prior to specifying the targeted competence in ELT curriculum, FLEP specifies the aims and policies of using and learning a foreign language (Payne & Almansour, 2014). That being the case, the representation of MC in ELT education should be explored considering both FLEP documents and ELT curricula. However, such an investigation of ELT curriculum has remained under-researched both in FLEP research and in ELT curriculum studies. With regard to FLEP, previous research has centered on specifying English as the medium of instruction (Sergeant & Erling, 2011), the necessity of FLEP (Tinsley, 2019), and preserving national language in light of multilingualism (Vogl, 2017). Specifically, in the context of the present study, research on FLEP has been limited to probing coherency and transparency of ELT policies (Atai & Mazlum, 2013; Davari & Aghagolzadeh, 2015; Kiany et al., 2011) and investigating FLEP dimensions (Kiany et al., 2011; Tajeddin & Chamani, 2020). On the other hand, studies on the representation of culture as a competence in ELT curriculum have mostly focused on integrating culture in bilingual education (Carstens, 2015), intercultural dimensions (Byram & Wagner, 2018), and critical cultural awareness (Baker, 2008) in ELT curriculum, all of which disregard MC.

Investigating the representation of MC in ELT curriculum is specifically needed at higher education level since the English users' first language (L1) cultural conceptualizations have been formed till that level, and they might be willing to encode such conceptualizations while using the English language, especially the ones studying English as a specialty at higher education. However, research on Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students, which are the curricula under analysis in the present study, has ignored MC. These studies either focused on the overall quality of General English courses (e.g., Mirhosseini et al., in press), which is a very small part of ELT at higher education with mostly unmotivated learners, or on English for Academic Purposes (e.g., Soodmand

Afshar & Movassagh, 2016; Tavakoli & Tavakol, 2018), in which the chances of conveying cultural conceptualizations are few. Additionally, the curriculum for ELT as a specialization at higher education has been studied from the limited perspectives of, for instance, reflecting on teaching and assessing English (Farhady et al., 2010) and proposing a socioculturally-informed syllabus to meet the writing needs of Iranian undergraduate English as a Foreign Language (EFL) students (Mallahi & Saadat, 2018), none of which has focused on MC. However, consideration of MC in ELT deserves further attention. According to Sharifian (2013b), English users' inability to explicate their own cultural conceptualizations and/or understand their interlocutors' encoded cultural schemas, cultural metaphors, or cultural categories might lead to miscommunication and misunderstanding. "[M]ore proficient' speakers are those who have been exposed to, and show familiarity with, various systems of cultural conceptualizations, participating with flexibility in EIL communication and effectively articulating their cultural conceptualizations when their interlocutors need this to be done" (Sharifian, 2009, p. 249). In order for ELT curricula to help learners achieve such a competency level, they need to focus on MC (Dabbagh, 2017; Sharifian, 2013b). To address these issues, the current study investigates the extent to which components and principles of MC are represented in Iranian FLEP and ELT curricula for undergraduate students. To this aim, the following research questions were formulated:

1. To what extent is MC addressed in major national policy documents of Iran?
2. To what extent is MC addressed in Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students?

2. Background

2.1. Metacultural competence (MC)

Sharifian (2013b) proposed MC that allows interlocutors "to negotiate their cultural conceptualizations during the process of intercultural communication" (p. 9) and "develops as a result of exposure to and familiarity with various cultural conceptualizations" (Sharifian, 2018b, p. 2). MC encompasses three components: 'cultural variation awareness', 'conceptual explication strategy', and 'conceptual negotiation strategy'.

As elaborated by Sharifian (2017), cultural variation awareness is the awareness that "one and the same language could be used by different speech communities to encode and express culturally specific conceptualizations" (p. 105). For instance, Iranian speakers of English might encode their cultural schema of "EXTENDED FAMILY (FÂMIL) when using the English word 'family',

which, however, commonly refers to ‘the nuclear family’ only” (Noshadi & Dabbagh, 2015, p. 59). Going beyond awareness, conceptual explication strategy empowers interlocutors to elucidate and clarify those conceptualizations that are thought of as unfamiliar to other interlocutors. Clearly, the ability to explicate conceptualizations presupposes interest in, and willingness to, learn about discrepancies in cultural conceptualizations (Sharifian, 2018b; Xu, 2017b). To clarify cultural conceptualizations, language users may resort to different strategies, including using a loan word along with a short explanation, paraphrasing (Kashgary, 2011), and non-verbal strategies (Schluer, 2021). Finally, in an act of communication, both sides might need to negotiate the intercultural meanings of a particular expression related to a particular cultural conceptualization. This would necessitate conceptual negotiation strategies in order to “seek conceptual clarification when one feels that there might be more behind the use of a certain expression than is immediately apparent” (Sharifian, 2018b, p. 4). Thus, this strategy presupposes cultural variation awareness and cultural explication strategies (Xu, 2017b). Examples of cultural negotiation strategies include using repair strategy, giving time to other interlocutors to explain their viewpoints on a particular cultural conceptualization (McKay, 2009), and striving to reach a consensus on cultural conceptualization discrepancies via arriving at a co-constructed, hybrid conceptualization (Sharifian, 2016).

To develop MC, Xu (2017a) proposed the required principles of ‘acknowledge’, ‘anticipate’, and ‘acquire and accomplish’. The first principle refers to appreciation of the change in the profile of English in terms of becoming pluricentric and world lingua franca, which in some cases involves speakers of varied cultural backgrounds. The second principle, i.e., ‘anticipate’, encourages the expectation that English can be used to express various cultural conceptualizations which might be different from the ones owned by native speakers. This variation necessitates that current English users become familiarized with different systems of conceptualizing experience and their negotiation which, in turn, captures the ‘acquire and accomplish’ principle.

Since the aim of the present study is to investigate the representation of MC in FLEP and Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students, in what follows, recent related empirical studies are briefly reviewed.

2.2. Previous studies on MC

Thus far, there have been few studies in terms of development, elaboration, and application of MC. These studies have mostly focused on online written intercultural communication (Xu, 2017b), reading comprehension (Schluer, 2021), textbook evaluation (Dabbagh & Atai, 2022; Sahraee Juybari & Bozorgian, 2020), and translation studies (Hrystiv, 2020; Kianbakht, 2020).

With respect to ELT curriculum, MC has recently been introduced as a possible target competence besides communicative competence. In this regard, Noshadi & Dabbagh (2015) suggested Applied ELT as a benchmark to enhance MC in class via proposing 'cultural experience sharing tasks', 'cultural schema awareness raising tasks', 'cultural categories concept mapping tasks', and 'cultural metaphor comprehension tasks'. Quite recently, Dabbagh (2017) proposed the implementation of MC, as an alternative to native speaker competency, to Iranian ELT curriculum in order to enable learners negotiate their own cultural conceptualizations using the English language. This change was suggested to take place from the level of the educational policy making through adapting the national policy documents down to teacher education programs and materials development via instantiating different Iranian as well as non-Iranian cultural conceptualizations centering on the same or different concepts.

3. Method

3.1. Corpus

Since the educational system of Iran is centralized, there is a top-down format of policy development and planning. Therefore, the documents related to the purpose of the present study are originated from two main stages of curriculum development, namely the policy stage (FLEP documents) and the planning stage (ELT curricula for undergraduate students) both of which have been developed in Persian.

Policy stage documents: The highest policy document in Iran, which was issued by the Supreme Leader in 2003, is *The 20-Year National Vision* based on which other policy documents were developed by The Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution. This council develops policy documents both for school education and higher education. More specifically, this council issued *The National Curriculum* and *The Fundamental Reform in Education Document* for school education and *The Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap*, *The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, *The Cultural Engineering Document*, and *The Islamicization of Universities Document* for higher education. In the present study, all the aforementioned documents, which are related to ELT either directly or indirectly (see Table 1), were selected for analysis since the formation and establishment of cultural conceptualizations are initiated from childhood and continue to be (re)conceptualized throughout the lifetime of individuals (Sharifian, 2011); and therefore, MC might be reflected in ELT-related statements within these documents.

Table 1
The Corpus of Policy Documents at the Policy Stage

Policy Document	Year of Development	Developer Organization	Reference to ELT
<i>The 20-year National Vision</i>	2003	Supreme Leader & Expediency Council	Indirect
<i>The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages</i>	2009	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & Ministry of Science, Research, and Technology (MSRT)	Direct
<i>The Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap</i>	2010	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Indirect
<i>The Fundamental Reform in Education Document</i>	2011	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution and Ministry of Education	Direct
<i>The Islamicization of Universities Document</i>	2011	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Indirect
<i>The National Curriculum</i>	2013	Ministry of Education	Direct
<i>The Cultural Engineering Document</i>	2014	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution	Indirect

Planning stage documents: At the planning stage, the active curricula designed and developed by MSRT for undergraduate ELT programs in Iran were analyzed. These documents are approved and issued for Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL), English Language and Literature, and English Translation Studies all at continuous B.A. programs (see Table 2). These documents include the purpose of the programs, the list of courses along with objectives, course content, assessment procedure, and suggested sources to be covered (based on the official website of MSRT¹).

The courses offered in these curricula are of three main types, namely general courses (The Persian Language, Physical Education, and Islamic Ideology courses), basic courses (skill-based courses and basic translation courses), and technical courses related to each area of expertise (TEFL, Literature, and Translation Studies).

Table 2

The Corpus of Policy Documents at the Implementation Stage

ELT Curriculum Document	Year of Development	Developer Organization	Reference to ELT
<i>Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in English Language and Literature</i>	2009	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Direct
<i>Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in TEFL</i>	2007	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Direct
<i>Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in TEFL</i>	2021	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Direct
<i>Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies</i>	2017	Supreme Council of Cultural Revolution & MSRT	Direct

3.2. Analytical framework for content analysis of documents

Sharifian's (2013b) components of MC and Xu's (2017a) three principles for developing this competence reviewed above were applied to the policy documents as the basis for analysis. As mentioned in the review section, MC "develops as the result of . . . the awareness that one language, e.g., English, can be used by different communities of speakers to express their [local] cultural conceptualizations" (Sharifian, 2014, p. 59) using the components of 'cultural variation awareness', 'cultural explication strategy', and 'cultural negotiation strategy' and

in light of the three principles of 'acknowledge', 'acquire and accomplish', and 'anticipate'. These models were utilized in order to reveal whether MC is appreciated and/or implemented in the major national policy documents of Iran as well as Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students. Figure 1 schematically represents these frameworks.

Figure 1.
Schematic Representation of MC

3.3. Data collection procedure and data analysis

In order to extract the representations of MC in the documents under analysis, deductive coding (Patton, 2015) was applied to the documents. In doing so, a coding scheme was developed by the first researcher based on Sharifian (2013b, 2017, 2018a,b) and Xu (2017a). Instances of reference to the elements and principles of MC were coded using *MAXQDA* version 2020. Since the documents under analysis were dissimilar in terms of purpose and length, setting a single unit of analysis was not possible for all the documents. Therefore, the assigned codes, which represented MC components and principles, covered diverse text segments, such as a phrase, a sentence, or a paragraph. In order to ensure the credibility and trustworthiness of the conducted content analysis, three Ph.D. holders of Applied Linguistics, who were experienced in working with qualitative data and *MAXQDA*, were asked to independently code 25% of the data after participating in a thirty-minute briefing session about the utilized framework. *Phi*-coefficient analysis of the obtained results revealed a high inter-coder agreement of 0.92 for the extracted MC components and principles.

4. Findings

Analysis of the Iranian major national policy documents revealed few, and in some cases indirect, instances of reference to the components of MC as well as its principles. Figure 2 and Table 3 represent the distribution of MC, in general, and with respect to its components and principles among the documents analyzed, in particular.

As can be seen, MC is most frequently represented in *The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages* (The thicker line in Figure 2 represents higher frequency).

This is quite natural since this document is the only policy document in Iran in which English language education is dealt with in detail.

Figure 2.
Distribution of MC Among Major National Policy Documents

Mostly, the components and principles of MC are instantiated rather generally, without representing a clear and straightforward application possibilities to ELT in Iran at the higher education level. For instance, in the introductory subsection of *The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages, the English language* is considered as a tool to encode and convey the culture of both native and non-native speakers of English.

Table 3
Frequency of MC Components and Principles Represented in Major National

MC		MC							Total
		The 20-year National Vision	The Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap	The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages	The Cultural Engineering Roadmap	The National Curriculum	The Fundamental Reform in Education	The Islamicization of Universities	
Components	Cultural variation awareness	0	0	11	1	1	1	0	14
	Cultural explication strategy	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	3
	Cultural negotiation strategy	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Acknowledge	0	0	5	0	1	0	0	6
Principle	Anticipate	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	4
	Acquire and Accomplish	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

(1)

The English language is the language of the human culture and civilization in general and western culture and civilization in particular. All people round the globe have access to non-western cultures (European-American) through the medium of the English language (*Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, p. 193).

(2)

A culture, a civilization, a scientific domain, a topic, even a superstitious belief system that plans to influence the world will not be successful

unless it uses the English language (*Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, p. 193).

Though these excerpts represent culture in its general sense of the term without considering the specific notion of cultural conceptualizations, they rather indirectly refer to the cultural variation awareness component of MC and the principle of acknowledgement concurrently. That is, these excerpts embrace the idea that the English language can be used by non-native speakers in order to encode their local cultural themes. Elsewhere in the same document, it is indirectly claimed that, besides confronting the western culture, the local culture should be maintained in teaching the English language.

(3)

Most countries have chosen learning the English language, rather than translating it; or at least they have changed their official language or the language of instruction at schools and universities into the English language. [...] However, perhaps integrating these two [approaches] and maintaining local language and culture while teaching the English language would be the best alternative (*Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, p. 194).

Though the phrase “maintaining local language and culture while teaching the English language” in the excerpt above can be interpreted in different ways, it can also set the preliminaries for the introduction of MC to Iranian ELT at higher education level. That is, according to excerpts 1-3, Iranian ELT learners can use the English language to encode their local cultural conceptualizations and maintain their local language and culture. However, in the process of codification of L1 cultural conceptualizations, it seems that the policy documents have targeted the cultural conceptualizations constrained to the Islamic ideology (see 4 below).

(4)

Teaching foreign languages provides the ground for *perception and understanding of intercultural interactions* and conveyance of scientific achievements via oral, visual, and written forms of the language to achieve various purposes *in light of the Islamic System as the criterion* (*The National Curriculum*, p. 3, emphasis added).

The above excerpt introduces Islamic ideology as the criterion for intercultural communication via the English language. Taking a cultural linguistic perspective, it can be postulated that *The National Curriculum* of Iran attempts to limit itself to Islamic themes as the cultural conceptualizations to be encoded

via the English language. However, *The Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages* sets both religious and national themes to be identified, selected, and represented in the ELT curriculum.

(5)

Identifying factors and sub-factors of the religious and national identity and reflecting them in the selection and development of the content [of ELT curricula] (*Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, p. 20).

Unlike cultural variation awareness, the other components of MC are not emphasized in the major policy documents except for a general reference to the significance of explicating local cultural themes in foreign language education (6) and explicating the cultural category of SACRED DEFENSE (the term Iranian government uses to refer to Iran-Iraq war) to speakers of other languages (7). These excerpts also encompass the cultural variation awareness component and the principle of anticipation in that, prior to explicating the aforementioned conceptualizations to English users, one needs to be aware of and anticipate the point that these cultural conceptualizations can be encoded using the English language.

(6)

Adjusting the content of foreign language education courses to the cultural and dialectal conditions of different areas in Iran (*Support for Comprehensive Scientific Roadmap in the Area of Languages*, p. 18).

(7)

Producing and promoting literature, poems, stories, and novels in the domain of Islamic Revolution and sacred defense and translating these literary works into other languages (*The Cultural Engineering Roadmap*, p. 72).

“Adjusting” the course descriptions to Iranian intracultural variations and “producing” literature to convey the ideology of the Islamic Revolution and the sacred defense demand the ability to explicate these cultural conceptualizations. However, the analyzed documents do not represent any related explicit strategy. Therefore, the promotion of cultural explication strategy is implicitly referred to in these documents. What is more, though the analyzed documents emphasize the significance of intercultural interaction in academic and political domains, they disregard the possible factors behind cultural misunderstanding in intercultural communication. According to cultural linguistics, one of such factors is the lack of ability to explicate and

negotiate L1 cultural conceptualizations. It might be axiomatic that development in cultural negotiation and explication strategies can improve the possibility of success in intercultural communication in terms of conveying local cultural conceptualizations. However, no single sentence about such development was found in major national policy documents.

In comparison to the policy documents, Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students represent MC more directly though no explicit reference to this term was found. Figure 3 and Table 4 depict the distribution of MC in these curricula. As can be seen, the recently revised curricula for B.A. in TEFL and Translation Studies are linked with MC with thicker lines, which shows that these curricula deal with this competence more than the other two.

Figure 3.

Distribution of MC in Iranian ELT Curricula for Undergraduate Students

The analyzed ELT curricula reflect the preparation of undergraduate students of English to use the English language in order to encode and convey Iranian culture and values of the Islamic Revolution (8 -10) as well as the cultural category of SACRED DEFENSE (11). Hence, these curricula follow the 'acknowledge' and 'anticipate' principles of MC as well as the component of cultural variation awareness, though these documents view the MC principles with the lens of Islamic Revolution ideology.

Table 4
Frequency of MC Components and Principles Represented in Iranian ELT Curricula for Undergraduate Students

		MC					Total
		Curriculum for Continuous B.A. in English Language and Literature	Curriculum for Continuous B.A. in TEFL	Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. in TEFL	Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. in Translation Studies		
Component	Cultural variation awareness	4	1	8	6	19	
	Cultural explication strategy	4	1	4	6	15	
	Cultural negotiation strategy	3	1	1	0	5	
Principle	Acknowledge	0	1	2	1	4	
	Anticipate	3	0	3	5	11	
	Acquire and Accomplish	0	0	0	0	0	

(8)

It is necessary that translators be educated in a way that they can [...] translate the values of the Iranian society and the Islamic Revolution and the Iranian culture and literature for the Western societies (especially through the English language as the medium for many linguistic, cultural, and political communication these days) (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies*, p. 4).

(9)

Using original scientific resources and state-of-the-art technology, being active in international events, forming productive international communication, representing religious and revolutionary values of our country are but few instance of the use of the English language in today's world (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in TEFL*, p. 4).

(10)

Graduate students should be able to convey Iranian art, literature, and culture as well as Islamic thoughts to other countries (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies*, p. 6).

(11)

Enhancing students' ability in using these concepts [i.e., resistance] in order to convey the achievements of Iranian history, especially the era of sacred defense against Iraq invasion (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies*, p. 67).

Reference to the verbs "introduce", "represent", and "convey" in the above excerpts reflects that the ELT curricula under analysis move beyond cultural variation awareness and appreciate the explication and negotiation of cultural conceptualizations, though no direct reference is made to particular cultural conceptualizations. That is, reference is made to "Iranian culture" and "Islamic thought" rather than specific Iranian or Islamic cultural schema, cultural metaphor, or cultural category. Such a perspective is also reflected in the translation of idioms as in (12) below:

(12)

Ability in translating culture-specific items, including idioms, proverbs, binominals, etc. [from English to Persian and vice versa] (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies*, p. 76).

Cultural variation awareness and cultural explication strategies are dealt with rather generally in (12) above. That is, though translating culture-specific idioms and proverbs from Persian into English requires the awareness that the English language can be used to encode Iranian cultural conceptualizations, no such conceptualization is emphasized. Additionally, the "ability" to do so demands explication strategies. However, similar to cases in 8-11, no such strategy is mentioned explicitly in the curricula.

As Table 4 depicts, the principles of "acknowledge" and "anticipate" underlie the three components of MC though in varying frequencies. However, the principle of "acquire and accomplish" is not dealt with in the analyzed curricula. This gap shows that familiarity with different systems of cultural conceptualizations is not welcomed in these curricula except for the imposed Islamic and Iranian ones, e.g., sacred defense mentioned in (7) above. That is, the Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students do not encourage them to learn and negotiate foreign systems of cultural conceptualizations.

Figure 4 provides a comparison between the representation of MC in Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students and the major national policy documents. As can be seen, quite similar to the findings of the analysis of policy documents, very few instances of the representation of cultural explication and cultural negotiation strategies were found in undergraduate ELT curricula. Dealing with these components of MC is limited to using the English language

to discuss Iranian cultural customs and superstitions (*Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in English Language and Literature*, p. 19), introducing and clarifying Iranian culture and Islamic thoughts to foreign nations (*Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in English Language and Literature*, p. 6; *Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in Translation Studies*, pp. 4 & 6; 8-9 above), untranslatability of religious texts due to cultural notions (*Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in TEFL*, p. 30), the role of media in conveying cultural values (*Revised Curriculum for Continuous B.A. Program in TEFL*, p. 39) with no reference to the required strategies for explication and negotiation of the possible cultural conceptualizations that might be encoded.

Figure 4.

Comparison of the Representation of MC Components and Principles Between Iranian ELT Curricula for Undergraduate Students and Major National Policy Documents of Iran

5. Discussion

The present study investigated the extent to which MC is addressed in major national policy documents and Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students. To investigate the formulated research questions, the selected documents underwent content analysis utilizing Sharifian's (2013b, 2018a,b) and Xu's (2017a) componential model and principles of developing MC, respectively. Deductive coding of the data revealed that MC was represented in both sets of documents rather generally without specifying its components and principles in detail. With regard to major national policy documents, most of the representation of MC was limited to the component of cultural variation awareness and the acknowledge and anticipate principles while cultural explication strategies were barely highlighted and cultural negotiation strategies and the acquire/accomplish principle were completely absent. On the one hand, it seems that the developers of Iranian major national policy

documents may have presupposed that MC is automatically achieved as a by-product of cultural variation awareness. However, lack of reference to cultural explication and cultural negotiation strategies in major national policy documents might leave EFL stakeholders with difficulty in identifying the possible sources of communication disruption in intercultural encounters let alone resolving them (cf. Schluer, 2021). Therefore, awareness of cultural variation is not sufficient for proficiency in current use of the English language (Sharifian, 2009); rather, learners should be familiar with explication and negotiation strategies, including repair strategies, devoting time to arrive at a co-constructed cultural conceptualizations (Sharifian, 2016), paraphrasing (cf. Kashgary, 2011), and non-verbal strategies (cf. Schluer, 2021). On the other hand, the partial representation of MC depicts incoherent policies in the realm of language and cultural conceptualizations in Iran and, as Mirhosseini and Khodakarami (2016) asserted, no vivid image of ELT objectives can be achieved as a result of such policy segments. This is quite in line with Byram and Wagner's (2018) observation that the appreciation of interculturality in ELT curricula has been limited to its understanding rather than its practice.

Despite the aforementioned issues, not only does such partial representation of MC reflect what Kiany et al. (2011) highlighted as the integration of cultural values in FLEP, but also it can be considered as the first step towards preventing Iranian EFL learners of becoming decultured from their local languaculture (Ghadiri et al., 2015) via raising their awareness of the possibility of using the English language to negotiate their own culture to English language users. This cultural negotiation might include encoding Iranian cultural schemas, cultural metaphors, and cultural categories in English. However, according to the findings of the present study, such cultural negotiation was centered around Islamic Ideology in the analyzed documents with complete negligence of Iranian cultural conceptualization, which might be due to ethnic variety in the Iranian society that makes selection of cultural conceptualizations to be included in the major national policy documents a rather complex endeavor.

Though all the components of MC are represented in Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students, its principles are still underrepresented. Despite this partial representation, enhanced attention to MC components and principles was observed in the recently revised curricula for TEFL and English Translation Studies in comparison to the older versions for TEFL and the non-revised English Language and Literature curriculum. The MC in the revised Iranian ELT curricula for undergraduate students encourages domestication of ELT at higher education. Previous studies also highlighted the role of MC in helping EFL learners negotiate their home cultural schemas, cultural categories, and cultural metaphors without the possible risk of miscommunication (Dabbagh, 2017; Noshadi & Dabbagh, 2015). Also, it was

not surprising that MC was mostly emphasized in English Translation Studies in comparison to other curricula. As previous studies highlight, development of MC can assist translators in enhancing their translation quality (Hrystiv, 2020; Kianbakht, 2020) which makes it necessary for translation students to become metaculturally competent.

Despite the aforementioned issues, the underrepresentation of MC in major national policy documents and ELT curricula for undergraduate students can be considered a big gap in Iranian ELT at the higher education level. That is, on the one hand, the aforementioned gap gains significance when we consider Kirkpatrick's (2012) call for the necessity of expressing local cultures using the English language and Sharifian's (2009) suggestion to include the ability to understand and negotiate cultural conceptualization systems encoded in English. On the other hand, the English language is experiencing a denationalization process around the globe and, as a result, various systems of cultural conceptualizations are gradually receiving permission to be encoded in English (Sharifian, 2018a) as a result of the emergence of EIL and its widespread use in intercultural communication (Matsuda, 2012; Sharifian, 2009).

Recent studies in the context of Iran have revealed the emerging variety of Persian English not only in daily interaction (Babaii et al., 2020; Sharifian, 2010a,b) but also in academic communication (Keshavarz, 2020) in which Iranian cultural conceptualizations are encoded in the English language. However, as the findings of the present study revealed, the appreciation of encoding cultural conceptualizations in the English language as a result of MC development was limited to negotiating Islamic cultural conceptualizations rather than conceptualizations related to the Iranian or non-Iranian cultures.

This selective representation reflects a hidden curriculum (cf. Kelly, 2004) in which the ELT curricula are designed to prepare EFL learners to negotiate the cultural conceptualizations germane to the Islamic Republic ideology, such as the cultural category of SACRED DEFENSE, while there are numerous Iranian cultural conceptualizations, e.g., cultural schemas of NOROUZ (Sahraee Juybari & Bozorgian, 2020), ABERU (Sharifian, 2013a), and TA'AROF (Beeman, 2020), among others, about which these curricula remain silent. However, research showed that in order to educate professional graduates, higher education needs to appreciate and practice familiarization with different forms of cultural exchanges (Lantz-Deaton, 2017). Applying this issue to the context of the present study, Iranian EFL learners would not limit themselves to using the English language to negotiate conceptualizations related to the Islamic Revolution; rather they need to communicate their own local cultural conceptualizations via the English language in their daily communication.

6. Conclusion

The present study investigated the representation of MC in Iranian FLEP and ELT curricula for undergraduate students. The findings revealed partial consideration of MC components and principles mostly regarding developing the ability to negotiate Islamic ideology and the relevant cultural conceptualizations, in complete negligence of Iranian ones, which reflects the presence of a hidden curriculum. This suggests implications for ELT curriculum developers and policymakers in Iran, including the incorporation of MC in ELT curricula for higher education. However, the perception and/or attitudes of Iranian ELT stakeholders, i.e., policymakers, curriculum developers, university instructors and learners, were not investigated in the present study with regard to the implementation of MC in ELT curriculum. Such studies await future investigations. Moreover, this line of inquiry can be complemented via exploring the appropriate Iranian or Islamic cultural conceptualizations to be negotiated through the English language by Iranian EFL learners.

Note

1. <https://www.msrt.ir//grid/283>

Authors' Statement

This study is extracted from Ali Dabbagh's PhD dissertation. Ali Dabbagh collected and analyzed the data and wrote up all the sections of the paper. Esmat Babaii, the supervisor of the dissertation, contributed to section 5 and provided comments on the whole paper. Mahmood Reza Atai, the advisor of the dissertation, contributed to section 2 and also provided comments and worked on sections 1, 2, and 3.

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